

A simple and sensitive spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) in various environmental samples

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A simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method is proposed for the determination of vanadium in traces, which is based on the oxidation of 4-nitrophenylhydrazine to 4-nitrophenyldiazoniumchloride with vanadium(V) in strong hydrochloric acid medium. The diazonium salt is subsequently coupled with phloroglucinol to give a reddish orange coloured dye having maximum absorption at 440 nm. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.2–2.0 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are $5.12 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0022 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of trace amount of vanadium in steel, soil, leaf, river and polluted water and biological samples.

A large number of methods have been reported for the trace determination of vanadium based on coloured complexes with organic reagents of some hydroxamic acids¹, such as *N*-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid², benzohydroxamic acid³, *N*-phenylcinnamohydroxamic acid⁴, 8-hydroxyquinoline⁵, 3-hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-4*H*-chromen-4-one (HL)⁶, 4-nitrophenylhydrazine and *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine⁷. In the present investigation oxidation of 4-nitrophenylhydrazine has been done in 6 *M* hydrochloric acid to form 4-nitrophenyldiazoniumchloride, which is subsequently coupled with phloroglucinol in basic medium to form reddish orange colour dye having absorption maxima at 440 nm.

The method of using phloroglucinol as coupling agent has been successfully applied for the determination of vanadium in vanadium steel and added quantities of vanadium in soil, leaf, river and polluted water and in biological samples, and the results have been compared with an earlier method⁷ where *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine had been used as the coupling agent together with 4-NPH.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of the dye showed λ_{max} at 440 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 5–50 μg of V^{V} per 25 ml of the final solution (0.2–2.0 ppm). The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $5.21 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0022 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The reproducibility of the method was checked by analysing 25 μg vanadium per 25 ml for a period of seven days. The standard deviation and relative standard deviation were found to be ± 0.0107 and 2.5%, respectively.

It was observed that 2 ml of 0.02% 4-NPH and 0.5 ml 6

M HCl are optimum for complete oxidation of 0.02% 4-NPH to 4-nitrophenyldiazonium chloride at $\sim 60^\circ$ for 5 min. Maximum absorbance value was obtained when 2 ml of 0.05% phloroglucinol was added followed by 1 ml of 1 *M* NaOH. pH of the final solution was 12.0–12.5. The time period of 15–20 min was necessary for the completion of the colour reaction.

The effect of various foreign ions, which are likely to interfere in the determination of vanadium, was studied and known amount of diverse ions were added and vanadium was determined as recommended. The tolerance limits (ppm) of different foreign ions in a solution containing 25 $\mu\text{g}/25 \text{ ml}$ of vanadium were found to be : F^- , SO_4^{2-} , Li^+ , NH_4^+ (4950); PO_4^{3-} , Ba^{2+} , Zr^{4+} (2050); Al^{3+} , Mo^{6+} , Ti^{4+} (950); NO_3^- (850); Co^{2+} (400); Cr^{3+} , W^{6+} (250); Fe^{3+} (150); Cu^{2+} (50).

Experimental

A Systronic 106 spectrophotometer, a Systronic 335 pH meter were used. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled deionised water was used throughout the study.

Stock solution of vanadium was prepared by dissolving of ammonium metavanadate (0.4592 g; E. Merck) in distilled water, a few drops of 6 *N* H_2SO_4 added, heated up to 80° , then few drops of KMnO_4 added and the volume was made up 100 ml. Vanadium was determined titrimetrically⁸ using KMnO_4 .

A 0.02% (w/v) 4-nitrophenylhydrazine (E. Merck) solution was prepared in 0.5 *M* HCl. A 0.05% (w/v) phloroglucinol (B.D.H.) solution was prepared in distilled water. 1 *M* NaOH was used.

Procedure : To an aliquot of sample solution containing 5–50 μg of V^{V} was added 4-NPH solution (2 ml) and acidity was maintained adding 6 *M* HCl (0.5 ml). The solution was then kept in a water bath ($\sim 60^\circ$) for 5 min. The solution was cooled and 0.05% phloroglucinol (2 ml) was added followed by 1 *M* NaOH (1 ml). The mixture was gently shaken and the volume was made up to 25 ml with double-distilled water and set aside for 15–20 min. The absorbance of the reddish orange colour dye was measured against the reagent blank at 440 nm.

Determination in steel sample : A weighed quantity of a high speed steel sample No. B.S. 4659 (1989) (W, 6; Mo 5; Cr, 4; V, 2%) containing about 1 mg of vanadium, dissolved in 40% nitric acid, was slowly evaporated to dryness and then treated with conc. HCl (0.5 ml). Brown yellow precipitate of hydrated tungstic acid along with other insoluble residue was filtered off. The filtrate was again evaporated to a small volume and the process repeated 2–3 times by adding of HCl and then diluted to 250 ml. In three 10 ml aliquot of this solution the vanadium contents was determined by the present method and also by the earlier method⁷; the results on the average are 1.95 and 1.91%, respectively, against the certified values 2%.

Determination in soil : Three soil samples (each 1 g) spiked with known amount of vanadium (30 μg) were fused with sodium carbonate and evaporated to dryness after adding water (25 ml). The dried material was dissolved in water, filtered and analysed by the present and earlier method⁷.

Determination in plant leaf : To three samples (each 2 g) of dried leaves spiked with known amount of vanadium (10, 20, 30 μg) were digested with potassium sulfate (0.2 g) and HNO_3 (10 ml). Then conc. HNO_3 (10 ml) was added and heated to dryness. The process was repeated 2–3 times for complete oxidation of the sample. The residue was treated with 1 : 3 dil. HNO_3 (25 ml), digested on water-bath for 30 min to hydrolyse polyphosphate to orthophosphate, then evaporated to dryness and the residue dissolved in hot water. The solution was then filtered and vanadium content was determined by the present and earlier method⁷.

Determination in river and polluted water : Shivnath river water samples (each 100 ml) from up-stream and down-stream were analysed for vanadium. They tested negative. To these samples known amounts of vanadium (15, 20, 25 μg) were added and analysed for vanadium. Similarly, polluted effluents from nearby iron and steel industry were collected and vanadium content was determined by the present and earlier method⁷.

Determination in biological samples : To three human blood samples (each 5 ml) spiked with known amount of vanadium (25 μg) were mixed with HNO_3 (~ 5 ml) and potassium sulfate (~ 5 g) and then heated to dryness. The

process was repeated 2–3 times. Then HNO_3 (1 : 3, 25 ml) was added to the residue and digested on a water-bath for 30 min. The content was again evaporated to dryness and the residue dissolved in distilled water filtered and cooled¹⁰.

Determination in urine : Three samples of urin (each 50 ml) were concentrated to 5 ml before treatment as describe above and analysed by the present and earlier method⁷.

In all the above cases almost 100% vanadium was recovered by the present and by the earlier method⁷ with standard deviation of 0.38 and 0.541, respectively.

Table 1. Comparison with other spectrophotometric methods

Sl. no.	Reagent	Medium / pH	λ_{max} nm	Beer's law range ppm	Remarks
1.	<i>N</i> -Phenylbenzo-hydroxamic acid method ^a	5–9 <i>M</i> HCl	510	2.4–7.8	Ti^{IV} , Zr^{IV} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} interfere
2.	Benzohydroxamic acid ^b	pH 1 2–5.5	450	2 8–8.2	Fe^{II} , Mn^{II} , Al^{III} interfere
3.	<i>N</i> -Phenylcinnamo-hydroxamic acid ^c	2.7–7.5 HCl	540	1.6–7.2	Ti^{IV} , Mo^{VI} interfere
4.	8-Hydroxyquinoline ^d	0.7 <i>M</i> HCl	430	1.0–5.00	Extractive, Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} interfere
5.	3-Hydroxy-2-(4-methoxyphenyl)-6-methyl-4 <i>H</i> -chromen-4-one ^e	0.12 <i>M</i> CH_3COOH	400	0.23–2.45	Extractive, Mo^{VI} , Sn^{II} interfere
6.	4-NPH and <i>N</i> -(1-naphthyl-ethylenediamine) ^f	5–8 <i>M</i> HCl	550	0.80–3.00	Oxidants, reductants, Cu^{II} interfere
7.	Present method	pH 12.0–12.5	440	0.20–2.00	Simple, selective, more sensitive, less interference

^aRef. 2. ^bRef. 3. ^cRef. 4. ^dRef. 5. ^eRef. 6. ^fRef. 7.

Conclusion : The present method has been compared with other spectrophotometric methods reported for vanadium (Table 1) and found to be simple, selective and more sensitive than other spectrophotometric methods.

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